

Overlapping Diabetes and Obesity Burden in Greater Houston Was Associated With Social Vulnerability and Low-Income, Low-Access Status

Yash N. Ganatra, Michael E. DeBakey High School for Health Professions, Houston, TX

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Abstract

Introduction

Diabetes and obesity are major public health concerns influenced by social and environmental conditions. This census tract-level study of Greater Houston investigated whether estimated diabetes and obesity burden overlapped and whether high-burden overlap tracts aligned with social vulnerability and Low-Income, Low-Access (LILA) status.

Methods

Publicly available tract-level diabetes and obesity prevalence estimates, Social Vulnerability Index (SVI) percentiles, and LILA indicators were harmonized to 2010 census tracts using area-weighted crosswalks. High-burden overlap tracts were identified as those in the highest 20% for both diabetes and obesity prevalence. Analyses included the Mann-Whitney U test, chi-square test, risk and odds ratios, Spearman correlation, Global Moran's I statistic, Getis-Ord G_i^* local cluster analysis, and threshold sensitivity analysis.

Results

Among 1,065 analyzed tracts, 162 were identified as high-burden overlap tracts. These tracts had higher median SVI (0.9475 vs 0.6185, $P < .001$) and were more likely to be LILA tracts (risk ratio, 2.3524; 95% confidence interval, 1.7404-3.1795). The combined diabetes-obesity score correlated strongly with SVI (Spearman $\rho = 0.872$, $P < .001$) and clustered spatially (Moran's $I = 0.7189$, $P = .001$). Getis-Ord G_i^* analysis identified 241 nominal local high-cluster tracts, of which 183 remained significant after False Discovery Rate (FDR) adjustment.

Conclusion

High-burden overlap tracts in Greater Houston were spatially clustered and associated with social vulnerability and LILA status. Tract-based identification of overlapping burdens may help prioritize public health resources toward communities with higher estimated burden and support the evaluation of socioeconomic conditions alongside estimated disease burden to aid in public health planning.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus; Obesity; Social Determinants of Health; Socioeconomic Factors; Geographic Mapping

Introduction

Diabetes and obesity are major public health challenges linked to heart disease, stroke, and other complications. Past studies have shown them to be clustered and linked with neighborhood socioeconomic conditions^{1,2}. Mapping tract-level clusters can identify communities that could benefit from prevention and care efforts³.

The association of Social Vulnerability Index (SVI), a composite of community vulnerability indicators, with prevalence of diabetes, obesity, inactivity, and chronic diseases has been previously explored. A countrywide census tract-level analysis showed that high SVI tracts had higher prevalence of diabetes, obesity, and physical inactivity⁴. Further, tract-level Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) variables have been used to investigate new-onset type 2 diabetes from a neighborhood context⁵.

While greater neighborhood fast-food exposure has been associated with higher risk⁶, another study argued that the effects extend beyond simple store access⁷. Conversely, food-environment pathways were not established as the mediators between disadvantaged socioeconomic conditions and diabetes risk⁸. While dynamic food environments may influence diabetes prevalence⁹, local spatial analyses may reveal geographical patterns that global models may inadvertently miss¹⁰.

Although prior studies have examined chronic disease patterns and socioeconomic conditions, fewer studies have mapped overlapping high diabetes and obesity burden in urban areas. The present study tested three hypotheses for the overlapping burden of diabetes and obesity in Greater Houston. First, high-burden overlap tracts (those in the highest 20% for both estimated diabetes and obesity prevalence) were expected to have higher social vulnerability versus the other tracts. Second, high-burden overlap tracts were expected to have a higher likelihood of Low-Income, Low-Access (LILA) tract classification. Finally, the combined diabetes-obesity score was expected to show spatial clustering, including both overall spatial autocorrelation and statistically significant local high clusters.

Methods

Study Area

The present study was an ecological, cross-sectional, census tract-level spatial analysis in the nine-county Greater Houston Metropolitan Statistical Area (MSA). These nine counties included Austin, Brazoria, Chambers, Fort Bend, Galveston, Harris, Liberty, Montgomery, and Waller (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The study area covering Greater Houston, showing the census tracts and the nine counties of Austin, Brazoria, Chambers, Fort Bend, Galveston, Harris, Liberty, Montgomery, and Waller. Source: U.S. Census Bureau. TIGER/Line shapefiles¹¹.

Data Sources and Variables

Publicly available datasets from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), and the United States Census Bureau were downloaded on March 7, 2026. Harmonization of these datasets, mapping, and statistical analyses were conducted during March 2026. Diabetes and obesity prevalence estimates were obtained from CDC PLACES 2025¹². This dataset provides model-based, small-area estimates of chronic disease measures for the US census tracts. Small-area estimates are useful for place-based public health research, but they should be interpreted as modeled estimates rather than direct clinical measurements of census tract disease prevalence¹³. The PLACES dataset includes estimates from the Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS). Its 2025 release includes 35 measures based on 2023 BRFSS and 5 measures based on 2022 BRFSS. The CDC/Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR) SVI 2022 dataset¹⁴ was used to obtain community-level social vulnerability data built from American Community Survey (ACS) 2018-2022 estimates. SVI is a variable that synthesizes several socioeconomic and demographic indicators. The overall SVI percentile variable (RPL_THEMES) was used in the present analysis. Food access was evaluated using the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) Food Access Research Atlas (2019) dataset¹⁵, specifically the LILAtracts_1And10 indicator, which identifies low-income census tracts with limited access to a supermarket, supercenter, or large grocery store using USDA's 1-mile urban and 10-mile rural distance measure. The LILA classification includes both economic and geographical dimensions of food access, but is not a complete measure of food affordability, food quality, transportation reliability, or household food insecurity.

Ethical Statement

This study utilized previously collected, publicly available government datasets. No new human data were collected, and no human participants were recruited, so Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was not required. In all the datasets, personally identifiable information was already removed prior to public release. Analyses were conducted only on aggregated census tract-level variables for public health research and planning purposes, not for clinical diagnosis or individual-level medical decision-making.

Data Preparation and Tract Harmonization

The PLACES tract-level dataset file was downloaded in Comma-Separated Values (CSV) format from the CDC PLACES portal and filtered to the nine Greater Houston counties using the 5-digit county Federal Information Processing Standards (FIPS) prefixes within the tract Geographic Identifiers (GEOIDs). The primary analysis used two PLACES measures considered in the study: diagnosed diabetes among adults and obesity among adults. The 2022 SVI dataset was obtained in CSV format from the CDC SVI portal. Values of -999 in certain SVI percentile fields were treated as missing.

The USDA Food Access Research Atlas 2019 dataset was obtained in Excel format from the USDA Economic Research Service website and filtered to the nine counties. Unlike the previous datasets, it used 2010 tract GEOIDs. Therefore, the 2020 to 2010 census tract crosswalk file was also obtained from the US Census Bureau¹⁶. Using this crosswalk, area-based weights were calculated from the ratio of the intersected land area to the total land area of the 2020 tract:

$$\text{Weight}_{2020 \rightarrow 2010} = \text{AREALAND}_{\text{PART}} / \text{AREALAND}_{\text{TRACT20}}$$

where,

$\text{Weight}_{2020 \rightarrow 2010}$ = area-based proportion of the 2020 tract assigned to the 2010 tract

$\text{AREALAND}_{\text{PART}}$ = land area of the intersection between the 2020 tract and the 2010 tract

$\text{AREALAND}_{\text{TRACT20}}$ = total land area of the 2020 tract

These weights were then used to convert the PLACES health indicators and the SVI percentile scores to the 2010 tracts with the harmonized value calculated as the weighted sum of the 2020 tract values:

$$X_{2010} = \sum (X_{2020} \times \text{Weight}_{2020 \rightarrow 2010}) / \sum (\text{Weight}_{2020 \rightarrow 2010})$$

where,

X_{2020} = value of a variable in the 2020 census tract (diabetes prevalence, obesity prevalence, or SVI percentile)

X_{2010} = harmonized value of that variable per the corresponding 2010 census tract

This approach allowed values from split or partially overlapping tracts to be proportionally allocated to the corresponding 2010 tracts. These converted estimates were merged with the LILAtracts_1And10 indicator and the 2010 tract boundary shapefile¹¹ to create the final, comprehensive analysis dataset. Any census tracts with missing diabetes prevalence, obesity prevalence, SVI, or LILA classification were removed. The comprehensive analysis dataset was used to generate the maps for this study. Each tract polygon contained the relevant health, social vulnerability, and LILA tract status variables. In order to visualize the spatial variation of those variables across the study area, choropleth maps were produced by assigning color gradients to the tract polygons based on the selected variables.

High-Burden Overlap Tracts and Combined Diabetes-Obesity Scores

Diabetes and obesity prevalence estimates were ranked separately across census tracts (Figure 2). The 80th percentile was chosen to identify relatively high-prevalence tracts while retaining a sufficient sample size for comparison. Accordingly, tracts in the highest 20% for diabetes were designated as high diabetes burden tracts, tracts in the highest 20% for obesity were designated as high obesity burden tracts, and tracts that met both criteria were classified as high-burden overlap tracts. A sensitivity analysis was performed by repeating the classification using the 75th- and 85th-percentile thresholds for both diabetes and obesity to determine whether the primary findings of the study were sensitive to this cutoff percentile.

Figure 2. Estimated diabetes and obesity prevalence by census tract in Greater Houston. Panel A shows estimated diagnosed diabetes prevalence, and Panel B shows estimated obesity prevalence. Tracts were grouped into six quantile-based categories, with each quantile representing approximately 16.67% of the tracts. Source: CDC PLACES 2025¹².

Diabetes and obesity prevalence were then standardized using z-scores calculated from the respective means and standard deviations as follows:

$$z = (X - \mu) / \sigma$$

where,

X = diabetes or obesity prevalence

μ = mean prevalence across all tracts

σ = standard deviation of the prevalence

For each tract, the z-scores for diabetes and obesity were averaged to create the combined diabetes-obesity score, a continuous variable that enabled subsequent statistical analyses. This average z-score was linearly rescaled to a 0-to-1 range, preserving rank order while making larger values consistently represent higher combined diabetes-obesity burden. Since diabetes and

obesity are often related in terms of behavioral and environmental determinants, this combined score represented their joint estimated prevalence with equal contribution from both conditions.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed in Python to test the three hypotheses using pandas, NumPy, and SciPy libraries. Similarly, GeoPandas and PySAL (libpysal and esda) were used for spatial analyses. Statistical significance was evaluated at the level of $\alpha = .05$. Then, the distribution of SVI percentiles (Figure 3) was compared for high-burden overlap tracts versus other tracts. Since SVI values are percentile rankings that may not follow a normal distribution, we ran the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test, which evaluated whether typical SVI percentiles were different for the two groups. A statistically significant test result would suggest that high-burden overlap tracts tended to have different social vulnerability levels as compared to other tracts. Accordingly, SVI percentiles (RPL_THEMES) were compared, and their medians and interquartile ranges were reported for the high-burden overlap tract and other tract groups. In addition, the relationship of combined diabetes-obesity scores with SVI percentiles was evaluated using Spearman rank correlation, which tests monotonic relationships between variables without needing a linear relationship or normal distribution.

Figure 3: Social Vulnerability Index (SVI) by census tract in Greater Houston, displayed using a choropleth map. Tracts were grouped into six quantile-based categories, with each quantile representing approximately 16.67% of the tracts. Source: CDC/ATSDR SVI 2022¹³.

We then investigated the association between the high-burden overlap tracts and LILA tract status using a 2×2 contingency table. Tracts were categorized into: high-burden overlap tracts versus other tracts, and LILA versus non-LILA. A chi-square test of independence was performed to determine whether the proportions of LILA tracts were different between the two

groups. Risk and odds ratios, with their respective 95% confidence intervals (CIs), were also determined to quantify the strength of the associations.

Spatial clustering of the combined diabetes-obesity score was tested using the Global Moran's I statistic. The analysis used the combined diabetes-obesity score and spatial weights based on Queen contiguity. The resultant parameter designates two tracts as neighbors if they share either a boundary or a corner. The weights matrix was row-standardized in order to make the influence of neighboring tracts add to one. Global Moran's I was calculated with 999 random permutations to estimate the statistical significance. A positive and statistically significant Moran's I value would indicate that census tracts with similar combined diabetes-obesity scores tended to cluster together geographically rather than being randomly distributed across the study area.

Finally, local Getis-Ord G_i^* analysis was performed using the combined diabetes-obesity score to identify statistically significant local high clusters. Queen contiguity spatial weights and 999 random permutations were used. Tracts with positive G_i^* z-scores and permutation P values of .05 or less were classified as nominal statistically significant high clusters. P values adjusted for False Discovery Rate (FDR) were also calculated as a sensitivity check across local tests.

Code Availability

The code used for data preprocessing, spatial analysis, statistical testing, and figure generation in this study is available at: <https://github.com/ynganatra/houston-census-tract-analysis>.

Results

The study area originally comprised 1,071 census tracts in the tract polygon layer. After merging the health, social vulnerability, and LILA tract status datasets, and removing the six tracts with missing key variables, the final mapped analysis dataset contained 1,065 tracts. As seen in Figure 2, the maps showed that both diabetes and obesity were not evenly distributed across Greater Houston and that areas of higher estimated prevalence overlapped primarily in parts of the Houston metropolitan area. The 80th-percentile cutoff for high diabetes prevalence was set at 17.26% and that for high obesity prevalence was set at 42.5%. As a result, 213 tracts were identified as high diabetes burden tracts and 217 tracts were identified as high obesity burden tracts. From these two sets, 162 tracts that met both criteria were classified as high-burden overlap tracts. Figure 4 demonstrated that these high-burden overlap tracts were concentrated mainly in Harris County, with a few high-burden overlap tracts in the outer portions of the study area.

High-Burden Overlap Tracts for Diabetes and Obesity

Figure 4: Diabetes-obesity high-burden overlap tracts in Greater Houston. Tracts in the highest 20% for both diabetes and obesity prevalence were classified as high-burden overlap tracts. The map highlights high-burden overlap tracts concentrated primarily in Harris County. Source: CDC PLACES 2025¹².

Per the first hypothesis, high-burden overlap tracts had higher social vulnerability than other tracts (Table 1). The median SVI was 0.9475 (interquartile range, IQR = 0.8962-0.9754) for the high-burden overlap tracts as compared to 0.6185 (IQR = 0.3309-0.8221) for the other tracts (Figure 5). This difference was statistically significant by the Mann-Whitney U test ($U = 132,976.5$, $P < .001$). The combined diabetes-obesity score showed a strong positive Spearman correlation with SVI ($\rho = 0.872$, $P < .001$). Thus, census tracts with higher combined diabetes-obesity scores also tended to be more socially vulnerable.

Table 1. Social vulnerability comparison for high-burden overlap tracts versus other tracts

Analysis	High-Burden Overlap Tracts	Other Tracts	Result
Tracts, n	162	903	-
Median SVI	0.9475	0.6185	-
SVI IQR	0.8962-0.9754	0.3309-0.8221	-
Mann-Whitney U test	-	-	$U = 132,976.5$; $P < .001$
Spearman correlation between combined diabetes-obesity score and SVI	-	-	$\rho = 0.872$; $P < .001$

Figure 5: Social Vulnerability Index (SVI) for high-burden overlap tracts and other tracts in Greater Houston. The boxplot compares SVI percentile distributions, with the median, interquartile range, and outliers shown. High-burden overlap tracts had higher SVI percentiles than other tracts. Source: CDC/ATSDR SVI 2022¹⁴.

According to the second hypothesis, LILA tract status differed between the high-burden overlap tract and other tract groups. Among high-burden overlap tracts, 46 tracts were classified as LILA tracts and 116 tracts were not classified as LILA tracts (Figure 6). Among the other tracts, 109 tracts were classified as LILA tracts and 794 tracts were not classified as LILA tracts. The association between the high-burden overlap tract status and LILA classification was statistically significant by the chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 28.14$, $P < .001$). The risk ratio was calculated as 2.3524 (95% CI, 1.7404-3.1795) and the odds ratio was 2.8886 (95% CI, 1.9443-4.2916). These results, summarized in Table 2, indicated that high-burden overlap tracts were more likely to be LILA tracts than the other tracts.

Table 2. Association between high-burden overlap tract status and LILA tract status

Tract Group	LILA Tracts	Non-LILA Tracts	Total
High-burden overlap tracts	46	116	162
Other tracts	109	794	903
Total	155	910	1,065
Chi-square test	-	-	$\chi^2 = 28.14$; $P < .001$
Risk ratio for LILA status	-	-	2.3524; 95% CI, 1.7404-3.1795
Odds ratio for LILA status	-	-	2.8886; 95% CI, 1.9443-4.2916

Overlap of High Diabetes-Obesity Burden and Low-Income, Low-Access (LILA) Tracts

Figure 6: Diabetes-obesity high-burden overlap tracts with respect to Low-Income, Low-Access (LILA) tracts in Greater Houston. The map classifies census tracts as high-burden overlap + LILA, high-burden overlap only, LILA only, or neither. Sources: CDC PLACES 2025¹² and USDA Food Access Research Atlas 2019¹⁵.

Per the third and final hypothesis, spatial autocorrelation analysis showed strong clustering of the combined diabetes-obesity score across the study area. The spatial clustering results are summarized in Table 3. The Global Moran’s I statistic was calculated as 0.7189 (P = .001, z-score = 41.31) (Figure 7). Local spatial analysis using Getis-Ord Gi* identified 241 nominal statistically significant high-cluster tracts at $P \leq .05$, of which 183 were significant after FDR adjustment (Figure 8). Of the 162 high-burden overlap tracts, 121 were nominal Gi* high-cluster tracts and 106 were within FDR-adjusted Gi* high clusters. This indicated that tracts with similar combined diabetes-obesity burden were located in the vicinity of each other more often than by chance.

Table 3. Spatial clustering analysis results for combined diabetes-obesity scores

Analysis	Result
Global Moran’s I	0.7189
Moran’s I permutation P value	.001
Moran’s I z-score	41.31
Nominal Getis-Ord Gi* high-cluster tracts	241
FDR-adjusted Getis-Ord Gi* high-cluster tracts	183
High-burden overlap tracts also in nominal Gi* high clusters	121 of 162 (74.7%)
High-burden overlap tracts also in FDR-adjusted Gi* high clusters	106 of 162 (65.4%)

Figure 7: Moran scatterplot for combined diabetes-obesity scores in Greater Houston. The upward trend and fitted line indicated positive spatial clustering, meaning high-score tracts near high-score tracts and low-score tracts near low-score tracts. Source: CDC PLACES 2025¹².

Figure 8: Getis-Ord G_i^* high clusters of the combined diabetes-obesity score in Greater Houston. FDR-adjusted G_i^* high-cluster tracts, nominal G_i^* high-cluster tracts, and high-burden overlap tracts that were not G_i^* high clusters are shown. Source: CDC PLACES 2025¹².

As seen in Table 4, sensitivity analyses performed using 75th- and 85th-percentile cutoff thresholds resulted in similar findings. In line with the expected trend, the number of high-burden overlap tracts increased to 214 for the 75th percentile and decreased to 118 for the 85th percentile. High-burden overlap tracts also had higher median SVI than the other tracts for both the sensitivity thresholds. The association between high-burden overlap tract status and LILA classification remained statistically significant and in the same direction. Finally, most high-burden overlap tracts remained concentrated in Harris County for the sensitivity analysis, supporting the same spatial distribution pattern as previously observed.

Table 4. Key sensitivity summary results using alternative overlap cutoff thresholds

Threshold Percentile	Classification	n	Median SVI	LILA Tracts, %	Risk Ratio for LILA Status
75th	High-Burden Overlap Tracts	214 (20.1%)	0.9380	28.5%	2.5806; 95% CI, 1.9401-3.4325
	Other Tracts	851 (79.9%)	0.5902	11.0%	
80th	High-Burden Overlap Tracts	162 (15.2%)	0.9475	28.4%	2.3524; 95% CI, 1.7404-3.1795
	Other Tracts	903 (84.8%)	0.6185	12.1%	
85th	High-Burden Overlap Tracts	118 (11.1%)	0.9519	28.8%	2.2551; 95% CI, 1.6231-3.1331
	Other Tracts	947 (88.9%)	0.6374	12.8%	

Discussion

The present study evaluated how diabetes and obesity co-occurred spatially across the Greater Houston study area. It also investigated whether the high-burden overlap tracts were associated with social vulnerability, LILA classification, and spatial clustering. The results demonstrated that both of these conditions were not evenly distributed across the study area and that areas of higher prevalence overlapped primarily in portions of the Houston metropolitan area. The primary findings of the study were insensitive to changes in the high estimated burden cutoff threshold, as sensitivity analyses using 75th- and 85th-percentile cutoffs produced similar geographical and tract-level associations.

Hypothesis 1: High-burden overlap tracts and Social Vulnerability

The first hypothesis proposed that the diabetes-obesity high-burden overlap tracts were expected to have higher social vulnerability levels as compared to other tracts, and this was supported by the results. High-burden overlap tracts had substantially higher SVI levels, with a median SVI of 0.9475 versus 0.6185 for other tracts. This difference was statistically significant, as demonstrated by the Mann-Whitney U test. The combined diabetes-obesity score also showed a strong positive Spearman correlation with SVI percentiles. These results were in line with prior studies that reported a strong association between neighborhood socioeconomic conditions and chronic disease burden^{4, 5}.

Hypothesis 2: High-burden overlap tracts and LILA tract status

The second hypothesis proposed that high-burden overlap tracts were more likely to be classified as low-income, low-access tracts and this was again supported by the results. The chi-square test of independence validated a statistically significant relationship between the high-burden overlap tract designation and LILA tract status. High-burden overlap tracts were more likely to be classified as LILA than other tracts based on the calculated risk and odds ratios. These results implied that the LILA status may represent an important aspect of neighborhood socioeconomic conditions associated with higher diabetes and obesity prevalence.

Hypothesis 3: Spatial Clustering of Combined Diabetes and Obesity Prevalence

The third hypothesis proposed that census tracts with higher combined diabetes-obesity scores were expected to show spatial clustering rather than being randomly distributed across the Greater Houston area. As with the other hypotheses, the analytical results strongly supported this hypothesis. The Global Moran's I statistic with its permutation P value demonstrated a strong positive overall spatial autocorrelation. Local Getis-Ord G_i^* analysis further identified statistically significant local high clusters, showing where high combined diabetes-obesity scores were spatially concentrated.

Public Health Implications

Local health agencies may utilize census tract-level spatial analysis, as illustrated in the present study, to identify areas where they can prioritize their limited resources for diabetes screening, nutrition, health education, and food access-related interventions. As a result, the agencies may be able to perform more geographically targeted planning by focusing on clusters of high-burden overlap tracts rather than individual tracts.

Limitations

Certain limitations may have influenced the results of the present study, and they should be addressed at this point. The CDC PLACES dataset consists of model-based prevalence estimates derived from survey data. Direct clinical measurements at the census tract-level are resource-prohibitive, and this limitation should be kept in mind when interpreting the results. In addition, this study was performed at the census tract-level, so its findings reflect community-level patterns, not individual cause-and-effect relationships.

The harmonization of datasets required the translation of census tract boundaries from the 2020 to 2010 definitions using area-based weighting. This crosswalk may have introduced some approximations that affected the results. The LILA indicator flag only represented a limited measure of food access conditions and did not capture affordability, quality, or reliability of transportation. Finally, the high estimated burden classification was set at the highest 20% of tract-level prevalence values, i.e., at the 80th-percentile. This cutoff threshold was not based on any nationwide benchmark for diabetes or obesity prevalence, although sensitivity analyses with 75th- and 85th- percentile thresholds did produce similar findings.

Conclusion and Future Work

In general, the results of the present study suggested a strong association of estimated diabetes-obesity overlapping burden with neighborhood socioeconomic disadvantage in the Greater Houston area. The study identified spatial clustering of the combined diabetes-obesity score, and

demonstrated that high-burden overlap tracts were associated with higher social vulnerability and LILA status. These findings help support the application of tract-level analysis to guide public health efforts and emphasize the importance of considering multiple overlapping risk factors at the community level. The three hypotheses of this study were supported by the statistical analysis results. This study was designed as ecological and cross-sectional and, hence, its findings should be interpreted as associations rather than cause-and-effect relationships.

Future research may help strengthen the findings of the present study. Longitudinal studies could be performed to evaluate whether changes in neighborhood socioeconomic conditions or food environments are dynamically associated with changes in the diabetes-obesity high-burden overlap tracts or their spatial patterns over time. Other neighborhood indicators, such as physical inactivity and access to health care services, could be studied to gain further insight into the study area. Additional spatial analyses using alternative local cluster definitions could be helpful to identify smaller subregional trends in the metropolitan region. A larger-scale comparative study of multiple metropolitan areas could help establish whether the trends observed in Greater Houston are reflected in other large cities as well.

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